
PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL SKILLS AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the extent to which principals' managerial skills predicted teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. In order to achieve the purpose of this study, two research objectives were structured, two research questions raised and two null hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The study adopted two theories: Managerial Skills Theory by Robert Katz (1955) and Theory of Performance Effectiveness by Don Elger (1972). Correlational research design was used for the study. The population for this study consisted of 2850 teachers in 150 private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East senatorial District. 285 teachers representing 10 % of the teacher's population were drawn to participate in the study using multi-stage sampling procedure. Two instruments entitled: "Principals' Managerial skills Questionnaire (PMSQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used to gather data for the study. The instruments were validated by three validates; two from The Department of Curriculum Studies, Educational Management and Planning and one from The Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha Reliability method with reliability indices of .798 and .737 for PMSQ and TJPQ respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in answering the two research questions and to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, principals' communication skill and principals' delegation skill are significant independent predictors of teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. Based on these findings, it was concluded that principals' managerial skills significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. It was recommended, amongst others that, Ministry of Education should prioritize the development of principals' managerial skills through targeted training programs, workshops, mentoring initiatives and policy frameworks. Suggestions for further research have also been made based on the findings of the study.

Keywords: Principals, Managerial Skills Teachers' Job Performance, Private Secondary Schools

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

School is a complex social organization, essentially characterized by formal structures and fabric of roles performed by people. It is not only a place where learners go to be educated but also a secondary agent of socialization. The school system in Nigeria is structured mainly into primary, secondary and tertiary education. Secondary education is the educational stage following primary school and preceding higher education or vocational training (Obiekwe *et al.*, 2020). It prepares students for college or university, technical or vocational training, or entering the workforce. Secondary education can be acquired either in private secondary schools or public secondary schools. A private secondary school is a secondary school that is not funded by the government. Instead, it relies on tuition fees paid by parents or guardians, and sometimes on other private sources like donations and levies for its financial support. Private secondary schools cannot function effectively if teachers are not motivated, competent, and committed to deliver high-quality instruction and create a supportive learning environment. This is to say that, when teachers perform their duty well, they contribute to a positive school culture, promoting a sense of community, respect, and responsibility among students which are critical factors in the proper functioning of secondary schools.

Teacher's job performance is also the measurement of the quality of instruction given to learners by teachers in the school which is rightly intended to improve accomplishment of the school. Buhera and Pasi, (2020) define teacher's job performance as how well teachers carry out their duties and responsibilities in the teaching and learning process, ultimately contributing to the achievement of school goals. This implies that teacher's job performance is not just about the quality of instruction, but also about how well the teacher can meet the needs of their students (Mawoyo and Dhliwayo, 2020). Dilshani and Hewanayake (2020) agreed that teachers can meet the needs of their students through lesson planning, classroom management, assessment, communication with students, parents, and colleagues, creating engaging learning environment, and building relationships with students. Teachers' job performance can be significantly influenced by principals' management skills. Effective principals possess strong management abilities that enable them to create a supportive and productive work environment, which in turn, enhances teacher performance. This means that, teachers cannot perform their job effectively if the resources in the school are not properly coordinated through the process called "management".

The person saddled with the responsibility of management in private secondary school is the principal. The role of a school principal includes the provision of instructional leadership, supervision of students' activities, disciplinary control, continuous evaluation and above all display of managerial skills to facilitate good teaching and learning conditions in school. Principals' managerial skills refer to the abilities and competencies that school principals possess to effectively manage and lead their schools. Akporehe and Asiyai, (2023) define principals' managerial skills as the special abilities principals possess to administer the schools which are usually attributed to training and practice. This implies that, principals must possess some specific abilities and competencies required for effective school leadership and management. These skills could enable principals to plan, organize, direct, and control the operations of a school, ultimately contributing to a positive and productive learning environment. It can also be said that, principals' managerial skills are set of behaviours that could lead to effective job performance and without them in many cases the knowledge of school principals may not have any effects. Akinfolarin, (2017) listed examples of principals' managerial skills to include leadership skill, communication skill, organizational skill, human resource management skill, problem-solving skill, conflict

resolution skill and instructional leadership skill. In the context of this study, communication skill and delegation skill are considered as the indices of principals' managerial skills.

It is believed that if principals possess certain managerial skills, they may likely influence teachers' job performance in private secondary schools. Private secondary schools may likely experience better teachers' job performance if principals motivate teachers, ensure effective communication, delegate duties to staff, involve teachers in decision-making, ensure effective interpersonal relationship and manage conflicts in the school. However, in some cases, this seems not so as some teachers are fond of going late for their classes, use ineffective or inconsistent teaching methods that don't engage students while others lack lesson planning and classroom management skills. These problems associated with teachers' job performance have been observed over the years. The researcher then wonders if this problem of teachers' job performance could be linked to the Principals' Managerial Skills of the various private Schools in Akwa Ibom State. It is against this backdrop that the study aims at establishing the extent of relationship between principals' managerial skills and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The persistence poor job performance of teachers particularly at the secondary school level has been a matter of concern over the years. It has been observed that some teachers seem going to class unprepared, grading assignments and exams inconsistently, setting unclear learning objectives for students, using teaching methods that fail to engage students. This poor job performance among teachers is also evidenced in lack of accountability, disorganized school environment, low student achievement, increased behavioral problems, low levels of student engagement, high operating costs, high rates of absenteeism, poor workload distribution, lack of standardization and poor data management.

Consequent upon this, one wonders if the way teachers perform their job is not a reflection of principals' managerial skills. It is worthy to note that some teachers are actually performing their job well while others are still lagging behind when actual performance is compared with expected performance. There have been several complaints from the government, public, institutional administrators, parents, fellow teachers and students about the way some teachers perform their job. Such complaints include lack of qualitative teaching, lateness to classes, poor attendance to school activities as earlier mentioned.

In the light of these observed problems, several researchers like Akporehe and Asiyai, (2023), Ibezim, (2024) and Abdul *et al.*, (2023) have carried out research related to teachers' job performance in secondary schools at various places and time, but these problems still persist. Moreover, the researcher observed that most variables used in the present study were not considered by other researchers. This has therefore created a gap in this study by trying to determine the relationship between principals' managerial skills (communication skill and delegation skill) and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which principals':

- i. communication skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.
- ii. delegation skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. To what extent does principals' communication skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District?
- ii. To what extent does principals' delegation skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

- i. Principals' communication skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.
- ii. Principals' delegation skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The study adopted two theories: Managerial Skills Theory by Robert Katz (1955) and Theory of Performance Effectiveness by Don Elger (1972). Katz's managerial skill theory is a theory that categorizes the competencies required for management by hierarchy and skill level. Katz noted that, managers need three basic skills in order to succeed in management position. These necessary basic skills are: technical skills, human skills and conceptual skills. The theory of performance effectiveness by Don Elger (1972) on the other hand develops and relates certain foundational concepts to form a framework that can be used to explain performance as well as performance effectiveness. This theory focuses on four tenets which are: to perform (to produce valued results); a performer (an individual or a group of people engaging in a collaborative effort); developing performance (a journey); and the level of performance (location in the journey). According to Elger (1972), humans are capable of extraordinary accomplishments and the level of teachers' performance depends holistically on six components namely: context, level of knowledge, levels of skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Principals' Managerial Skills

Principals' Managerial skills have been looked at by several researchers to include the abilities and competencies that school principals possess to effectively lead, manage, and administer schools. Suyatno and Santosa, (2022) define managerial skills as the special ability or expert talents of administrators to plan, organize, coordinate, control and direct the operation of an enterprise for the achievement of stated goals and objectives. It can be deduced that, principals' managerial skills are sets of skills, abilities and competencies that enable school principals to effectively plan, organize, coordinate, control, and make decisions to manage the school and its resources, ultimately achieving its educational goals. Hakim, (2016) listed examples of principals' managerial skills to include instructional leadership skills, communication skills, strategic planning skills, problem-solving skills, collaboration skills, decision-making skills, classroom observation skills and teacher support skills. In this study, principals' communication skill and principals' delegation skills are considered as the indices of principals' managerial skills.

Several factors influence a principal's managerial skills. These include their level of knowledge of managerial functions, such as planning, organizing, leading, and controlling, as well as their ability to effectively communicate, motivate, and build relationships with teachers and other staff. Additionally, factors like the school's context, including its size, resources, and the specific challenges it faces, can impact a principal's managerial effectiveness. Principals' managerial skills are crucial for effective school leadership and

student success. These skills enable principals to organize, plan, and lead the school effectively, ultimately impacting teacher performance, student achievement, and the overall school environment. Strong managerial skills help principals create a positive learning environment, manage resources efficiently, and foster a culture of continuous improvement.

2.1.2 Teachers' Job Performance

Teacher's job performance refers to the effectiveness and quality of a teacher's work in achieving educational goals and objectives. Uko *et al.* (2015) define teacher's job performance as teachers compliance to set standards and commitment to school vision and mission in order to achieve the goals and objectives of education It involves the extent to which the teacher participates in the overall running of the school in order to achieve the established goals and objectives of the school. It encompasses various aspects, including lesson planning, classroom management, assessment, communication, and creating a positive learning environment. Teachers' job performance could be measured through teacher's job satisfaction and job attitudes such as job commitment, feelings of job challenge, job meaningfulness and job responsibility (Esie, 2023).

Buhera and Pasi, (2020) considered key components of teachers' job performance which contribute to a teacher's overall effectiveness in creating a positive learning environment and fostering student growth. These components include classroom management, instructional delivery, assessment and feedback, planning and preparation, professional development, communication and collaboration. Okeke and Mbah, (2019) considered several factors that influence teachers' job performance, to include both internal and external elements. Internal factors encompass teacher characteristics such as personality, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, subject mastery and teaching competence, attitude and motivation. External factors that can influence teachers' job performance include school leadership, school culture, work environment, community involvement, professional development, rewards and recognition, classroom management, communication, assessment and feedback. The importance of teachers' job performance has a profound impact on student learning outcomes, academic achievement, and overall educational experience.

2.1.3 Principals' Communication Skill

Principals' communication skill refers to the ability of school principals to effectively exchange information, ideas, and messages with teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Sherman, (2015) identified certain principals' communication skill such as: open communication skill, inclusive communication skill, aggressive communication skill, assertive communication skill and autocratic communication skill. Open communication skill is where the leader consciously creates an atmosphere for all individuals within an organization express their views and opinions on issues affecting the running of the organization. Inclusive communication is where all staff members in the school feel free to get involved in the decisions that affect their day- to- day activities. An aggressive communication skill is one in which individuals express their feelings and opinions and advocate for their needs in a way that violates the rights of others. In assertive communication skill, people stand up for their right or other people's rights in a calm and positive way without being either aggressive or passively accepting 'wrong'. Autocratic communication skill involves downward communication and with the use of commanding tone. Lunenburg and Ornstein (2016) asserted that good communication skill leads to effective job performance. It encourages mutual exchange of ideas and fosters a commitment to collaborate and work as a group for the good of the organization. Nwankwo, (2015) proposed that principals must therefore have qualities that can enhance communication styles and facilitate administrative effectiveness.

2.1.4 Principals' Delegation Skill

Delegation means assigning certain responsibilities along with the necessary authority by a superior to his subordinate staff. Wang and Owens, (2017) define delegation skill of school principals as the ability of principal to entrust specific duties and decision-making power to subordinate staff, like teachers, to achieve school goals. According to Odike, (2018), there are basic skills of task delegation that principals can adopt. These skills include, tentative skill, controlling skill, participative skill and collaborative skill. Tentative skill is a delegation skill where principals are likely to be more frequently willing to delegate tasks or projects to others but may have several reservations. Controlling skill is a delegation skill where by principals are likely to give any task or projects to others on occasional basis. Participative skill is a delegation skill whereby principals are likely to delegate work frequently as a prime means to help other individuals work in teams and experience different tasks to which they may have had little or no previous exposure. Collaborative skill is a delegation skill where the principals are likely to make a much more careful assessment about the individuals who will benefit from delegated work and then offer a task to each person on a selected basis. There are some principles of delegation that principals may take into consideration when delegating task. These according to Patrick, (2020) are principle of: standards and outcomes, clarity of authority and responsibility, staff involvement, task completion, willingness and proficiency, adequate control measures, applicable authority and the unity of command. Patrick (2020) further observed that effective delegation skill is essential in creating high quality staff. Principals who delegate duties are able to coach, train and develop competent staff, thus making them more valuable to the organization.

2.2 Empirical Framework

2.2.1 Principals' Communication Skill and Teachers' Job Performance

A study was conducted by Odu-Dikoro, (2022) to examine the principals' managerial competencies and teachers' job effectiveness in public and private secondary schools in Delta State. Nine research questions were raised and seven hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. An ex-post –facto research design using correlational and descriptive method was employed for this study. The population of the study was 14,299 principals and teachers from public and Government approved private secondary school in Delta State. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in to select 715 secondary school principals and teachers for the study. Two sets of questionnaire titled "Principals' Managerial Competencies Questionnaire" (PMCQ) and Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ) were used for data collection. The face validity and reliability of the instrument was carried out. The reliability of the instruments was estimated using the split half reliability method which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.71 and 0.88 for the PMCQ and TJEQ respectively. The questionnaires were administered to 714 respondents in public and private secondary schools. However, only 630, which represent approximately 88% of the total number of administered questionnaires, was retrieved and used for data analysis. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistic and Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient(r) and coefficient of determination (r^2) were used to answer the research questions.

All hypotheses were tested using Product Moment Correlation coefficient at alpha level of 0.05. The findings of the study revealed principals' communication competency significantly relates with the level of teachers' job effectiveness of public and private secondary school teachers in Delta State. The reviewed study investigated the relationship between principals' communication competency and teachers' job effectiveness in public and private secondary schools while the present study examined the relationship between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools.

However, reviewed study was conducted in Delta State while the present study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the gap in the study.

2.2.2 Principals' Delegation Skill and Teachers' Job Performance

A study on principals' delegation function techniques and teachers' job performance was conducted by Olaifa *et al.*, (2024). A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Four research questions were raised to guide the study. The population for the study was 38 principals and 1604 teachers in the 38 public senior secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. The sample size for the study was 10 principals and 313 teachers. The instrument used in the gathering of data was a questionnaire titled "Principals Delegatory Functions and Teachers Job Performance Questionnaire". The questionnaire was developed on a five-point rating scale provided for the respondents to choose from. A test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument using the Cronbach Alpha method with a reliability coefficient of .91. The data obtained from the pilot study were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS and weighted mean. The finding of the study showed that principals' delegation functions and techniques were found to be effective in enhancing teachers' morale, meeting curriculum outlines, and achieving educational goals. Both studies are related in that both studies considered the relationship between principals' delegation of functions and teachers' job performance. However, the reviewed study was conducted in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State while the present study was conducted in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design was used for this study. The area of this study was Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. The population of this study consisted of 2850 teachers spread across the 150 private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North East senatorial District. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 285 teachers representing 10 % of the teacher's population sample size of the study. This selection was based on the assertion of Nwana (1981). Two self developed instruments by researcher entitled "Principals' Managerial skills Questionnaire (PMSQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used to obtain data from respondents. Items on PMSQ were developed in line with the constructs of the independent variable (communication skill and delegation skill.) to elicit data from teachers on principal's managerial skills. TJPQ consisted of 20 items. It was used to measure dependent variable (Teachers' Job Performance) and it was designed to obtain information from teachers about their job performance. Both instruments were constructed on a declarative statement. PMSQ was constructed on a four-point rating scale as follows: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed while TJPQ was constructed on a four point rating scale as follows: All the Time (ATT), Most of the Time (MOT), Some of the Time (SOT) and Not at All (NAA). Respondents were assured of confidentiality and were expected to indicate by ticking the extent to which the items applied to them in appropriate column.

The instruments developed were validated by three experts. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, inter-item method was used for "Principals' Managerial skill Questionnaire (PMSQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)". The instruments were administered once on 30 respondents from the population not selected for the study. The scores obtained from the exercise were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Reliability Analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in answering research questions and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Out of 285 instruments sent out, 273 copies were returned. This represents 95.8% return. Out of 273 instruments returned, 5

instruments were wrongly filled and were not useful for analysis. All completed and returned copies of the instruments were coded and subjected to statistical analysis. The decision rule by Schober *et al.*, (2018) was applied while answering the research questions to show the strength and direction of relationship between principals' managerial skills and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Research Question 1: To what extent does principals' communication skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District?

Table 4.1: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Principals' Communication Skill and Teachers' Job Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. N =268

Variable	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum xy$	Cal.-r	Remark
Communication Skills	4446	75088	176663	.150	Weak relationship
Teachers' Job Performance	10622	427690			

The entries in Table 4.1 reveal the type and strength of relationship between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance. The results reveal that the calculated r-value of .150 is weak and positive. Hence, the result implies that there is a weak and positive relationship between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

4.1.2 Research Question 2: To what extent does principals' delegation skill predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District?

Table 4.2: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Principals' Delegation Skill and Teachers' Job Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. N =268

Variable	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum xy$	Cal.-r	Remark
Delegation Skills	4484	76126	179931	.814	High relationship
Teachers' Job Performance	10622	427690			

The entries in Table 4.2 reveal the type and strength of relationship between principals' delegation skill and teachers' job performance. The results reveal that the calculated r-value of .814 is high and positive. Therefore, the result implies that there is a high and positive relationship between principals' delegation skill and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

4.2 Testing of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis 1: Principals' communication skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

Table 4.3: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Principals' Communication Skill and Teachers' Job Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District N=268

Variable	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	Decision at P < 0.05
Communication Skills	4445	75088	176663	.150	.014
Teachers' Job Performance	10622	427690			

*significant at P < .05 level, df = 268

The entries in Table 4.3 show the r-value of .150 with its corresponding P-value of .014 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance with 268 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that "Principals' communication skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District" is rejected. This result resolved that there is a significant relationship between principals' communication skill teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

4.2.2 Hypothesis 2: Principals' delegation skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

Table 4.4: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Principals' Delegation Skill and Teachers' Job Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District N=268

Variable	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-cal	Decision at P < 0.05
Delegation Skill	4484	76126	179931	.814	.000
Teachers' Job Performance	10622	427690			

*significant at P < .05 level, df = 268

The information in Table 4.4 reveals the r-value of .814 with its corresponding P-value of .000 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance with 268 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that "Principals' delegation skill does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District" is rejected. This result resolved that there is a significant relationship between principals' delegation skills and teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

4.3 Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study based on the research questions answered and the null hypotheses tested revealed the following:

- i. There is a weak and positive relationship between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.
- ii. There is a high and positive relationship between principals' delegation skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.
- iii. Principals' communication skill significantly predict teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.
- iv. Principals' delegation skill significantly predict teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Principals' Communication Skill and Teachers' Job Performance

The result of the analysis reveals a weak and positive relationship between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. The corresponding hypothesis reveals a significant extent of prediction between principals' communication skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. This result could be attributed to the fact that consistent communication from the principal reduces ambiguity and enhances coordination. A principal who uses appropriate channel of communication to convey information promptly can help teachers synchronize their efforts, share resources, and address problems collectively.

The finding of this study is at variance with Ayoro and Onyeike (2020) who in their study found that there was no significant relationship between principal's communication skills and teachers' productivity in Mission Secondary schools in Delta State. However, this result supports the finding of Fashiku (2016) who agreed that a significant relationship exist between leaders' communication pattern and lecturers' job performance. Furthermore, this finding corroborates Van de Linden's (2016) empirical investigation on the effects of leaders' communication on teachers' attitude to work among employees. This finding also supports the finding of Egboka and Alike (2018) which indicated that principals' application of communication skills was a significant correlate of teachers' job performance in secondary schools. When feedback is delivered with empathy and clarity, teachers are more receptive and can adjust their practice swiftly, accelerating their own development and, consequently, their students' learning outcomes. In summary, a principal's ability to communicate clearly, listen actively, coordinate effectively, and nurture a supportive environment creates the conditions under which teachers feel informed, motivated, and empowered.

4.4.2 Principals' Delegation Skill and Teachers' Job Performance

The result of the analysis reveals a high and positive relationship between principals' delegation skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. The corresponding hypothesis reveals a significant extent of prediction between principals' delegation skill and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. This outcome can be explained by the fact that delegation also sharpens role clarity. By explicitly outlining tasks and expected outcomes, the principal eliminates ambiguity, allowing teachers to focus on their core teaching responsibilities without being sidetracked by unclear or overlapping assignments.

This result is in agreement with Kongnyuy's (2020) who upheld that, delegation enhances school administration by encouraging teachers to seek new and inventive ways to teach while also increasing teacher engagement. The finding of this result also supports

Ndirangu and Mungai, (2024) who revealed that delegation of duties to teachers and principal's prompt feedback have an impact on teachers' job performance. Furthermore, the finding of this result supports Sani, (2020) who agreed that principals' delegation styles significantly influence teachers' job satisfaction. By distributing workload according to expertise and capacity, principals prevent burnout, ensure timely completion of tasks, and maintain a balanced workflow across the school. Teachers experience a more supportive environment where administrative burdens are manageable, allowing them to devote more time and energy to teaching and student support.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study was able to make various discoveries and observations about the extent to which principals' managerial skills predicted teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. The study establishes that when principals possess strong managerial skills, such as communication skill and delegation skill, teachers are more likely to exhibit higher levels of job performance. Teachers feel supported, valued, and empowered when led by a manager who communicates clearly, delegates thoughtfully, and fosters collaboration. This supportive climate reduces stress, enhances collegiality, and encourages teachers to innovate, persist, and invest fully in student success. It is therefore concluded that principals' managerial skills significantly predict teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Ministry of Education should prioritize the development of principals' managerial skills through targeted training programs, workshops, mentoring initiatives and policy frameworks.
- ii. Proprietors of secondary schools should invest in the continuous professional development of their principals, providing opportunities for them to attend leadership conferences, seminars, and workshops.
- iii. Principal of secondary schools should focus on developing and refining their managerial skills, recognizing that their leadership has a direct impact on teachers' performance and students' outcomes.
- iv. Teachers' job performance in private secondary schools may be different. Therefore, further research is needed to examine the generalization of these findings to public secondary schools.

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